

Annex 1 - Prep4Blue WP2 Workshop Report (14.9.2022)

WP2 Session Minutes: Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting Brussels, 14 September 2022

Overview: During the Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting on September 14 in Brussels, Belgium, Stefan Fritz and Wendy Namisnik from WP2 (Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces) co-led a PowerPoint presentation (see Annex III) on WP2's work for the project. This included a discussion of: tasks and deliverables (narrative guide, communication plan, social media campaign, website, events/exhibitions), goals and expected outcomes, timeline, linkages with other WPs and projects/initiatives, and short-term next steps. Stefan also provided a demonstration of the website (in draft stage), including a video featuring 360-degree technology that will be utilized in various areas of the site. Additionally, after the presentation, they led a working session with an abstract focus on Mission identity and narrative (see page 2 for WP2 Working Session Overview).

Key takeaways from audience engagement after the PowerPoint presentation:

- We should go really big with our “visionary narrative” – “rewilding” is an example.
- Our introductory website video was uninspiring considering we are trying to be visionary.
- We should change the imagery associated with negative connotations on the website, e.g., the fish in the nets.
- It's important to distinguish that it isn't necessarily the EC that has initiated this kind of restore our ocean and waters work; it is the scientist and researchers, the boots on the ground that have been doing this for years and are finally getting some funding.
- We should not feel a heavy burden to carry the Mission and the EC cannot comment on how forthcoming initiatives (e.g., tender) will affect our (overlapping) work, so we should continue on as it could be a year before anything happens.
- We, as Prep4Blue, should be recognizable as part of the Mission and partners should follow us on Twitter as some of our social media efforts have already started.

Clarifications: Important to note and that may have been misunderstood by the audience is that the website is in a draft stage and images were selected by the web developers without our input. They are all subject to change, and, ideally, images that demonstrate successes/failures should come from our partners, lighthouses, and other initiatives. The styling of the site with three themes demonstrating success vs. failure were well received and will be further developed so as not to offend Mission Ocean stakeholders (where possible).

Next Steps: In the short-term, our focus is on developing the narrative guide and launching the website. At the November Cork event we will likely hold another narrative workshop and re-shoot the website video to include more stakeholders and capture more dramatic footage/messaging. We're also in the process of contracting with a social media expert for the campaign and have created the Communications Cooperative (first meeting in Oct).

WP2 Working Session Overview

Following WP2's presentation on their Mission Ocean work, and as part of the WP2 working session, attendees were split into five groups based on the colors assigned to them for the event (purple, blue, green, orange, red). Each group was presented with the same 15 questions (see Annex I below) regarding assigning an identity to "Mission Ocean," specifically if it were a living being. The groups were given about 40 minutes to answer the questions, create a sketch of their vision of Mission Ocean based on their answers, and then later present their findings to all participants (see posters in Annex II).

The exercise was meant to get Prep4Blue partners to step away from the administrative concept of the Mission as simply "another European Commission project," and rather think creatively about it as force for change, an identity unto itself, a being that can present a story to the world on behalf of our ocean and waters to inspire change, commitment, and action for a better world. Overall, the activity (answers, drawings, presentations) will help inform WP2's work on the narrative and other communication deliverables as well as hopefully inspire all Prep4Blue partners to utilize creative approaches when communicating Mission Ocean.

Annex I: Working Session - Mission Ocean Identity Questions & Group Answers

1. Is it a gender? If so, which gender?
 - Gender neutral, gender free, non-binary, flexible
2. What kind of voice(s) do you hear when it speaks?
 - Inspiring, many voices/accents/languages, wise, peculiar, singing, dolphins, water running, whales
 - Cousteau, Attenborough, Adele
3. What does it look like?
 - Soft, circular, flowing, multi-organism, endless, chimeric creature – adapts to many goals and audiences, chameleon, sea/water/waves
 - Catamaran, lighthouse
4. What does it taste and smell like?
 - Fresh, damp, moist, healthy, oxygen, salty
5. What sounds does it make?
 - Melodical, whispering, musical, fresh, healthy
6. How does it feel to your touch?
 - Strength, liquid, fluid, soft, wet

7. What images do you see along with it?
 - Positivity, fish, deep sea, wind, mountains, sand and pebbles, changing color, both scary and inspiring
8. How does it make you feel emotionally?
 - Motivated
9. How does it make you feel physically? Which of your senses awaken and how?
 - Energized, exposed, scared, frustrated, would like to speak
10. What color(s) is it?
 - Teal, blue, reflective, shimmering, shiny, blue/multicolour, purple, green
11. What is it feeling?
 - Responsibility, adventurous, full of life, exploring, connection, harmony, friendship, peace, protective, safe
12. What does it want?
 - Action, participation, engagement
13. What message(s) is it sending you/the world?
 - Call to action, plea, emergency, hope, connect people
14. What makes it thrive versus suffer?
 - Collaboration, hugs, rivers, diversity, energy, food
15. Where does it come from & where does it go?
 - Come from common concern goes to people, from source to the ocean, from head to hands
 - Eternal circle, ancient

Annex II: Working Session - Group Presentation Posters

ORANGE

1. GENDER NEUTRAL
2. INSPIRING
3. SOFT, CIRCULAR
FLOWING
4. FRESH
5. MELODICAL
6. POWER/STRENGTH
7. POSITIVITY
8. MOTIVATED
9. ENERGIZED
10. TEAL
11. RESPONSIBILITY
12. ACTION, PARTICIPATION, ENGAGEMENT
13. URGENCY, PLEA, CALL TO ACTION
14. COLLABORATION
15. COMES FROM
COMMON CONCERN
GOES TO PEOPLE

GREEN

1. Non binary : male/female
2. Many voices / accents / languages / wise voice / peculiar voice
3. Multi organism creature / endless thing
4. Damp, moist taste
5. Whispering / musical sound
6. Liquid / fluid / soft / jelly / intangible
- 7
- 8
- 9
10. Blue / silver / shimmer / shiny
11. Adventurous / exploring / full of life
12. Connection / Harmony / Friendship / Peace
13. Justice / motivation / Hope / Connect people
14. Fair
15. From source to the ocean / From head to hands

RED

Community

What makes it things?
HUGS

Octopus Moustache
only the arms are ever
seen cleaning things up

The creature wants
to swim in
clean waters.

I'm IMPRESSED
WOW
WOW

BLUE (MUTE)
&
multicolor?

disorientation
(changes
grade and
color?)

Feeling:
SAFE
protection

Chimeric creature
to adapt to
many goals
and audiences.

WAVE
SOUND

≠ ATTITUDE
≠ FACET

Feeling:
Wet, softish

Cameleon changing
colors.

Feeling:
Calming
Relaxation

VOICE

→ Couscous

→ D. Attelborough

→ D. Adile

~~PURPLE~~

BLUE

*Gender-Free.
→ many languages
have gender for the
sea

WAVE

NOISES
→ singing, sirens.
→ dolphins
→ water running
→ whales. → laughing

TASTE
→ fresh air, oxygen.
salty,
→

SMELL
→ fresh.
→ healthy.

LOOKS
→ dynamic
→ sea, water, wave.
→ wave from all perspective
→

MISSION
→ teenager, a bit
lost. with activism
enthusiasm, energy.

FEELINGS it's
→ exposed. → scared
→ would like to speak
→ would like to act.
→ frustrated. like baby
because it can't speak

TOUCH
→ fluid.
→ warm
→

IMAGES:
→ fish, deep sea
→ wind
→ mountains.
→ sand + pebbles

Thrive?
→ energy. → bad.
→ rivers. → humans
→ diversity.

MISSION word.
Don't like it.
Bad connotation.
not bottom-up
→ not religious things

(What does it
wake you feel?)
→ peace or scared
(protecting or protected)
→ female feelings
→ hopeful.

IMAGES)
→ changing colour
→ both scary + inspiring
→

COMES FROM GOES TO:
→ eternal.
→ circle.
→ ancient

SUFFER
→ Ego
→ humans.
→ indifference / ignorance
→

We can
do it! Now!
Go blue and
green!

It's our
mission. We
will do it

CO²

Pentahelix actors

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

WP2 Overview

Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communication & Spaces

Stefan Fritz, Wendy Namisnik

Prep4Blue Kick-off Meeting

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prep4blue.eu | missionoceanwaters.eu

#MissionOcean #EUmissions #HorizonEU

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10. Short-term Next Steps
11. Narrative Brainstorming Session

Tasks & Deliverables

Tasks	Task 2.1. Narrative Guide	Task 2.2. Communication Plan	Task 2.3.1 Social Media Campaign (Pilot)	Task 2.3.2 Virtual Space (Website) (Pilot)	Task 2.3.3 Physical Spaces (Events/Exhibitions) (Pilot)
Deliverables	D2.1 Narrative Guide (M6)	D2.2 Communication Plan (M9)	D2.3 Interim Implementation Report On Tasks & Proposed Deliverables (M12)		D2.4 Final SWOT Analysis Of WP Product Implementation (M36)
Products & Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Narrative Guide 	Communication Plan	Social Media Campaign	Virtual Space (Website)	Two Exhibitions/Public Events In Iconic Spaces (e.g., Ocean Space Venice) With Artists, Designers, Architects, & Other Initiatives To Showcase The Mission & Its Contributors

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Goals & Expected Outcomes

Goals

- Create inspiring & accessible platforms for communicating the Mission.
- Increase stakeholder & citizen awareness about, & engagement with, the Mission.
- Promote the Lighthouses & their contributions (show the successes, highlight the impacts, encourage mobilization, & convey the principles/values of why we're doing this).
- Advocate for and assist with consistency in messaging/branding across Mission partners.
- Provide helpful tools, information, & support in Mission communication activities.

Expected Outcomes

- There is increased access to Mission information & therefore an actual increase in understanding of, and engagement with, the Mission.
- Prep4Blue partners, other CSAs, & Mission-related initiatives have & use the proper branding/messaging tools for instant recognizability and Mission cohesion.
- Stories that champion the Mission are published and circulated outside "echo chambers" for broader public appreciation, understanding, and engagement.
- Mission contributors & partners understand the larger effort they are part of & can more efficiently collaborate as well as articulate their work across audiences.

No one is left behind in the achievement of the Mission.

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Timeline

Narrative Guide & Communication Plan

- **Narrative Guide** – Identified ways to motivate, educate, & entertain through Mission stories
 - This guide should help partners tell captivating stories through a distinguished Mission communication style (tone, voice, & feel) to inspire & engage the public in the Mission.
- **Communication Plan** – A collection of tools (branding, imagery, rules, templates), information (links, channels, established guidelines), & recommendations (best practices) to convey messages to audiences across platforms while remaining true to the Mission brand.
 - The EC has already published a comprehensive communication strategy and source files, & our plan will pull heavily from those to advocate consistency among partners.

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Social Media Campaign - Pilot

Demonstrate a creative & successful campaign around a Mission subject(s) to drive engagement across audiences.

- Lighthouses, Blue Parks, & 3 Green Deal goals will be explored through themes.
- Early themes include: plastics waste, leisure/sports, nature restoration (including habitat and animal protection), & food.
- We'll engage with ECOPs & social media professional(s) to implement this task.

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Virtual Space (Website)- Pilot

Provide an attractive, informative, & easy-to-navigate website to learn about & engage with the Mission

- Cutting-edge, 360-degree videos featuring dynamic ocean/water actors in Mission landscapes (some linked to social media & events)
- Varied & dynamic content (stories, Lighthouse details/successes, event calendar, data, cinema, helpful links, etc.)
- Easy-to-use content management system; various partners may be able contribute directly
- Available in multiple languages (dubbing/language selection/auto-translate)
- May serve as main hub (one-stop-shop) through which all Mission-related initiatives are hosted or directly linked/accessible
- Could be absorbed by future Mission Implement Platform so information isn't lost (no need to "reinvent the wheel")

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Website Demo

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EU MISSIONS

RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

PROSPERITY

THE PROJECTS

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean commodo ligula eget dolor. Aenean massa. Cum sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus. Donec quam felis, ultricies nec, pellentesque eu, pretium quis, sem. Nulla consequat massa quis enim. Donec pede justo, fringilla vel, aliquet nec, vulputate eget, arcu.

Discover the Projects

THE MISSION

Cum sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus. Donec quam felis, ultricies nec, pellentesque eu, pretium quis, sem. Nulla consequat massa quis enim. Donec pede justo, fringilla vel, aliquet nec, vulputate eget, arcu.

Discover the Mission

Physical Spaces (Events/Exhibitions) - Pilot

“Market spaces” could showcase Mission contributions & successes, facilitate exchanging ideas, encourage public participation, & promote market creation. The first event will likely happen in Venice.

Ocean Space | Venice

Varvakeios Agora Market | Athens

Linkages

Establish the WP2 Communications Cooperative

- Goals & Objectives
 - Share information & solicit content/stories for development & promotion
 - Keep communication channels open among stakeholders so silos don't form
 - Provide tools, resources, recommendations, & support for communications activities
- Members
 - 1 representative from each Prep4blue WP
 - Alberto from CINEA & Natalia from Prep4Blue to be in CC
 - We will invite 1 contact from each Lighthouse & Blue Parks (CSAs)
 - Work collaboratively with the implementation platform & other relevant projects once established
- Structure
 - Mailing list
 - Shared folder to access tools/assets
 - Possible access to our website & social media channels to cross-promote (granted permissions, etc.)
 - Option for engaging local stories to be captured in campaigns (videos/photos, articles, social media, etc.)
 - Meetings &/or workshops may be held to serve a variety of wants/needs

Short-term Next Steps

- Communication Cooperative 1st Meeting (October 2022)
 - Access to tools/assets
 - General update on communication needs/wants/next steps
- Publish (within 3-6 months from today)
 - Narrative Guide
 - Communication Plan
 - Website
- Grow Our Social Media Presence & Capabilities
 - Continue to post regularly and acquire new stories & information (<https://twitter.com/eumissionocean>)
 - Hire social media intern to more actively manage channels/campaign
 - Contract with social media expert/advisor for campaign strategy & implementation

Ensure Recognizability & Maximize Impact

Narrative Brainstorming

Tell us about your vision of the Mission if the Mission was a living being.

1. Is it a gender? If so, which gender?
2. What kind of voice(s) do you hear when it speaks?
3. What does it look like?
4. What does it taste & smell like?
5. What sounds does it make?
6. How does it feel to your touch?
7. What images do you see along with it?
8. How does it make you feel emotionally?
9. How does it make you feel physically? Which of your senses awaken & how?
10. What color(s) is it?
11. What is it feeling?
12. What does it want?
13. What message(s) is it sending you/the world?
14. What makes it thrive versus suffer?
15. Where does it come from & where does it go?

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Annex 2 - Workshop Future Coast (10.11.2022)

Coast in Transition 2022

Mission-oriented research

Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung
German Marine Research Consortium

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What is the role of science in restoring our ocean and waters by 2030?

How much responsibility does science have, if it has access to the best available knowledge?

Motivation for this Session

The symposium „Küste im Wandel“ seeks to discuss:

... the increased need for **results and options for action from marine research** for sustainable coastal management.

... den erhöhten Bedarf nach Ergebnissen und Handlungsoptionen aus der Meeresforschung für ein nachhaltiges Küstenmanagement zu diskutieren.

KDM, as a representative of the interests of German marine research, needs:

research results, success stories, ideas for the future, etc. for its consultations with parliamentarians, government officials, industry associations, NGOs, as well as other societal groups.

KDM is a partner in the Prep4Blue EU project tasked with developing the narrative of the EU's Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

EUROPEAN UNION

EU MISSIONS

RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

Concrete solutions for our greatest challenges

#EUmissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

What Makes the iPhone so Smart?

Figure 13 from *The Entrepreneurial State: debunking public vs. private sector myths* (2015, p. 116)

Context for Mission-oriented Science funding and policy

Die größten Sorgen der Deutschen

welt

Quelle: EY Germany

EU Priorities in 2022

- implementing the European Green Deal,
- achieving a Europe fit for the digital age,
- delivering an economy that works for people,
- making Europe stronger in the world,
- promoting our European way of life, incl. when facing health crises,
- protecting and strengthening our democracy and defending common European values.

5 Missions to address societal challenges

Adaptation to Climate Change

Cancer

Climate-neutral and Smart Cities

Soil Deal for Europe

Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

How often does a Sustainable Development Goal appear in leaders' top six priorities?

We asked leaders the following question: "Based upon your experience, what are the most important issues for advancing [your country's] development?" Respondents identified up to six goals from a fixed list of 16 SDGs that they believed to be most important for advancing their country's development.

Horizon Europe – the key funding tool

- Implementation via a portfolio of actions, e.g. research projects, policy measures or even legislative initiatives to achieve goals that could not be achieved through individual actions.
- Funding: 500 Million to 2025
- Evaluation in 2023

The Ocean Mission – Goals, Structure & Resources

The Ocean Mission – Goals in Detail

PROTECT AND RESTORE MARINE AND FRESHWATERS ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

- Protect at least 30% and strictly protect 10% EU's sea areas
- Restore 25.000 km free flowing rivers
- Marine nature restoration targets (incl. degraded seabeds, coastal ecosystems)

PREVENT AND ELIMINATE POLLUTION OF OUR OCEANS, SEAS AND WATERS

- Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter
- Reduce by at least 30% microplastics
- Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, chemical pesticides

MAKE THE BLUE ECONOMY CARBON-NEUTRAL AND CIRCULAR

- Net zero maritime emissions
- Zero carbon aquaculture,
- Low carbon multipurpose use of marine space

NOTE: Funding is intended to support projects delivering these goals.

The Ocean Mission – Lighthouses

Lighthouses to pilot, demonstrate, develop and deploy Mission activities across EU seas and river basins

Baltic & North sea basin

MAKE THE BLUE ECONOMY
CARBON- NEUTRAL AND
CIRCULAR

Mediterranean sea basin

PREVENT AND ELIMINATE
POLLUTION OF OUR OCEAN,
SEAS AND WATERS

Danube river basin

PROTECT AND RESTORE MARINE
AND FRESHWATERS
ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

Atlantic & Arctic coast

Cancer Mission

By 2030, more than 3 million lives saved, living longer and better

Ensure Equitable Access

Prevent
What is
Preventable

Optimise,
Diagnosis &
Treatment

Support
Quality
of Life

Areas
of Action

Understand

Focus of KDM
Actions to
date:
Ensuring that
science is a
core part of the
mission

Support for
Project
Proposals

Calls approx.
120 Euros
Million/Year

More
Events

Influencing
the Narrative

Activities
implemented with
COM, BMBF/PT, DE-
Partner, EP, INT-
Partner

EC Proposal

G7 Coop
Ocean
Plastics Lab

Events

Exchanges
with Policy
Makers

The Contribution of KDM to Mission development

Task:

Creating a Visionary Narrative,
Communications & Spaces

Develop a strong Mission Narrative

Goal:

To showcase the value of
investing in ocean and coastal
science and innovation with a
view to shaping the future of
ocean policy and marine
research policy.

Prepare an overarching Mission
Communication Strategy

Designing and piloting innovative
physical and virtual Mission Spaces for
the Mission community and general
population, pilot website, pilot
exhibition, pilot social media campaign

What is the science narrative?

The contribution of science and innovation – the simplified version

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/exhibition/panoramas2022?s=03#3Ocean>

The contribution of science and innovation

The horrendogram "confused" reality

(1) In 2013 the WFD replaced the Dangerous Sub. Dir.; Freshwater Fish Dir.; Shellfish Waters Dir. & Groundwater Dir.

(2) The network of MPAs in England will consist of EMS/Natura 2000 (SACs & SPAs), SSSIs, Ramsar sites and MCZs

(3) The UK is not a signatory to this Convention however a number of public statements have been produced that confirm its endorsement of the rules in its Annex

All regulated activities in the English marine environment consider UK marine policy drivers such as the UK High Level Marine Objectives 2009, the UK Marine Policy Statement (4) and various National Policy Statements

The ease of understanding EU Commission press releases

The contribution of science and innovation – the DFG version

A "realistic" narrative, e.g. saving Venice

Sediment Transport

Seagrass/Salt marsh restoration

Seagrass modelling

Functional biodiversity modelling

Moses Barrier

What is our narrative
(account of
connected events)?

Our story?

... concerning the
contribution of
science to restoring
our ocean and waters
by 2030?

What KDM activities will we support with this narrative exercise?

Mission Pilot Social Media Campaign

Mission Pilot Website

Mission Pilot Exhibition

REST-COAST EU Project
Science Policy Briefings and Briefing Papers

KDM Strategy Group Multi-Use and MPAs

A narrative exercise

A narrative exercise

A multinational offshore wind farm operator is seeking to develop a coastal area for a new wind farm.

As a compensation measure, an equally large area adjacent to the wind farm is to be renaturalized.

The plan is to guide/support the design and implementation of both the wind farm and the renaturation area through scientific projects.

What could a scientific contribution to restoration look like?

Sample of Ocean-related topics in WP 2023-24 in Horizon Europe Cluster 6

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-2: Impact of light and noise pollution on biodiversity

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-5: Understanding and reducing bycatch of protected species

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-6: Restoration of deep-sea habitats

HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-7: Demonstration of marine and coastal infrastructures as hybrid blue-grey Nature-based Solutions

HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-8: Using automatic species recognition and artificial intelligence to fight illegal fish discards and revolutionise fisheries control

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-11: Novel culturing of aquatic organisms for blue biotechnology applications

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBio-01-10: Targeting aquatic extremophiles for sourcing novel enzymes, drugs, metabolites and chemicals

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-2: Integrated assessment and monitoring of emerging pollutants in the marine environment

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-3: Tackling human and climate change induced pollution in the Arctic - building resilient socio-ecological systems

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-2: Integrated assessment and monitoring of emerging pollutants in the marine environment

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-3: Tackling human and climate change induced pollution in the Arctic - building resilient socio-ecological systems

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-3: Ocean and coastal waters carbon- and biodiversity-rich ecosystems and habitats in Europe and the Polar Regions

HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8: Closing the research gaps on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) in support of global assessments

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-6: Ocean models for seasonal to decadal regional climate impacts and feedbacks

HORIZON-CL6-2024-COMMUNITIES-01-3: Participation and empowerment of Arctic coastal, local, and indigenous communities in environmental decision-making

HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-11: Reducing observation gaps in the land-sea interface area

HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-4: Supporting the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance and Declaration

Contacts in the KDM Secretariat (as of November 2022)

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Mikrobiologie & Biotechnologie

Blue Carbon
Biotech

JPI Oceans
- Blue Carbon
- Ocean Carbon Capacities
- Licht und Lärm

BMBF Finanziert

Dr. Jan-Stefan Fritz
Politikwissenschaften und Geographie

KDM-Gremien
Strategiegruppen
Internationales, insb. EU, UN, OECD,

NKP UN World Ocean Assessment

EU Mission Gesundes Meer

Atlantik Kooperation

Dr. Jella Kandziora
Ökonomie und Ingenieur

NKP G7 FSOI
Ozeanbeobachtung
Beziehungen zu BMBF und BMUV

JPI Oceans
- Plastik
- Verschmutzung

BMBF Finanziert

Sebastian Konitzer
Umweltmanagement und Verwaltung

Finanzen
Verwaltung
Multimedia

Wendy Namisnik
Kommunikation

EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"

Atlantik Kooperation
Nachwuchsvernetzung

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Koordination,
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Atlantikkooperation

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Ozeanbeobachtung
Küste und Blauer Ozean –Visualisierung der Arbeit der Strategiegruppen und der deutschen Beiträge

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Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften & Rohstoffe, Hannover

Centrum für Erdsystemforschung & Nachhaltigkeit, Uni Hamburg

Dep't Maritime Systeme Interdisziplinäre Fakultät, Uni Rostock

Deutsches Meeresmuseum, Stralsund

Deutsches Schiffahrtsmuseum, Bremerhaven

Forschungszentrum Küste, Hannover und Oldenburg

GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel

Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon

Institut für Chemie & Biologie des Meeres der Uni Oldenburg

Jacobs University, Bremen

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Hamburg, Rostock

Kiel Marine Science – Zentrum für Interdisziplinäre Meereswissenschaften an
der Christian-Albrechts-Uni zu Kiel

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Leibniz-Zentrum für Marine Tropenökologie, Bremen

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Survey - Your coastal research priorities "Options for Action"

The KÜNO-Symposium has as a goal to promote dialogue results and options for action for sustainable coastal management.

This survey is in preparation for the session "Options for Action - Science contributions to ocean and coastal missions" (Thursday, 13:45). We would like to better understand how your scientific work and/or engagement is contributing to goals articulated in the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030".

Join us in the session "Options for Action" to see and discuss the results of this survey!

Please note: All of your information will be anonymous and used for discussion purposes only.

To which of these three policy objectives does your work contribute?

Protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems.

Prevention and elimination of plastic, nutrient and chemical pollution.

Multi-use of marine space in a sustainable and carbon neutral manner.

What do you think is the role of scientists in implementing these policy objectives?

Please complete the following sentence with the answers below. Multiple answers are possible.

Do you think scientists should ... :

... describe and/or understand the state of the ocean and coasts.

... give advice on the current and/or future state of the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... join societal actors in protecting the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... work with industry to maximise jobs and economic development in the ocean and coasts based on the best available knowledge.

... fully integrating understanding and action into research projects.

Options for Action - Restoration Project Design

The Challenge

A multinational offshore wind farm operator is seeking to develop a coastal area for a new wind farm. As a compensation measure, an equally large area adjacent to the wind farm is to be renaturalized. It is planned to guide the design of both the wind farm and renaturation area through scientific projects.

The Task

What could a scientific contribution to the restoration effort and the wind farm design look like?

Create a short title/acronym for your post.

Please use 5 characters maximum.

To which of these three policy objectives do you contribute?

Protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems.

Prevention and elimination of plastic, nutrient and chemical pollution.

Multi use of marine space in a sustainable and carbon neutral manner.

At what point in the process does your contribution come into play?

Scientific foundation building

Providing advice

Co-designing

Co-implementing

Evaluating

List three keywords that characterize the contribution.

Please use commas to separate words.

